

**BRIDGING THEORY AND PRACTICE: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL EXPLORATION
OF PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS' INTERNSHIP
AT MANUEL A. ROXAS HIGH SCHOOL**

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative phenomenological study investigated the lived experiences of five pre-service teachers from Adamson University during their teaching internships at Manuel A. Roxas High School in the academic year 2022-2023. The study aimed to identify the challenges faced and the professional growth experienced by these Pre-Service Teachers. This study used Clark Moustakas' phenomenological reduction in data analysis. It was used to reflectively analyze the narratives of the five Pre-Service Teachers in Manuel A. Roxas High School. Utilizing in-depth interviews, the research explored themes such as adaptability and resilience, mentorship and support, professional identity development, and challenges in student engagement. Results revealed that pre-service teachers faced significant challenges in adapting to diverse learning environments and managing classroom dynamics. However, these challenges facilitated substantial personal and professional growth, enhanced by supportive mentoring from cooperating teachers. The study underscores the importance of experiential learning in teacher education, highlighting the crucial role of mentorship and the need for emotional resilience. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the complexities of teaching internships, offering insights that can help improve pre-service teacher training programs to better prepare candidates for the demands of the teaching profession.

Keywords: *Pre-Service Teachers, Teaching Internship, Educators, Student-Teachers*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching is often referred to as a noble profession due to its vital role in shaping the minds and futures of individuals (Fendrik & Antosa, 2017). Teachers have the power to inspire, educate, and empower students, making it a profession that requires high moral standards and a deep sense of responsibility. The importance of a teacher's personality and professionalism cannot be undermined, as it directly impacts the overall learning experience of students (Sukawati et al., 2020). A good teacher with a strong personality will be able to cultivate positive relationships with students and create an environment that fosters growth and learning. Furthermore, a teacher's good personality also extends to their relationships with other colleagues and members of the school community. Nevertheless, they all must begin proper teaching training during their collegiate years to realize these attributes. They are called pre-service teachers or student teachers rendering their internship in different educational institutions.

A teaching internship is a period of supervised practical experience in a school or educational setting, where pre-service teachers can apply their theoretical knowledge. They work closely with experienced teachers called cooperating teachers to develop and enhance their teaching skills, while also gaining valuable insights into the realities of the profession. During the teaching internship, pre-service teachers are given the opportunity to observe and participate in planning, delivering, and assessing lessons. They also have the chance to interact with students, collaborate with colleagues, and reflect on their practice. Through the teaching internship, pre-service teachers can develop a deeper understanding of the complexities of teaching and gain hands-on experience in creating a positive learning environment for students. The teaching internship is an essential part of the pre-service teacher's education and serves as a bridge between their academic coursework and future career as a professional educator.

Pre-service teachers in the Philippines undergo a comprehensive program that prepares them for the teaching profession may it be in the private or public educational institutions. Different universities offered educational courses that prepare future educators in the field of the academe. In Adamson University, the course of Bachelor of Secondary Education with specialization in English is offered to hone future educators. The curriculum being followed adheres to the CHED prescribed teaching curricula. With this matter, teaching internship is a crucial part of the program. Pre-service teachers are trained in classroom instruction, practical teaching experiences, and assessments to ensure that they have the necessary knowledge and skills to become effective educators. They are also required to constantly engage in continuous professional development through various means, such as attending seminars, participating in professional organizations, and seeking additional qualifications. These efforts are aimed at equipping pre-service teachers with a strong foundation in pedagogy, subject matter knowledge, and professional ethics. Through their internship experiences, pre-service teachers in the Philippines can apply their learning in a real classroom setting and gain valuable hands-on experience.

However, various challenges are met by pre-service teachers as they journeyed their teaching internship in the schools. During these times, they face various challenges that test their abilities, skills, and commitment to the profession. These challenges may include managing classroom dynamics, adapting to diverse learning needs, effectively utilizing teaching resources, and maintaining strong communication with parents and colleagues. Additionally, student teachers may also face challenges in incorporating technology and innovative teaching methods into their lessons, as well as balancing the demands of lesson planning and assessment. Moreover, some conflicts may arise between them and their respective cooperating teachers. Through these challenges, the internship serves as a valuable opportunity for prospective teachers to develop their understanding of the teaching profession and enhance their skills in a practical setting. The researcher was interested in the teaching internship journeys of five pre-service teachers as they rendered their services in Manuel A. Roxas High School from the school year 2022-2023. This study explored the challenges faced by the student teachers in the school's stakeholders.

Literature Review

Experiential Learning

Learning by doing is a concept coined by John Dewey, which emphasizes the importance of practical, hands-on experiences in education. During the teaching internship, pre-service teachers can put this philosophy into practice by actively engaging with students, implementing instructional techniques, and reflecting on their experiences (Stephens, 2011). Furthermore, this hands-on experience allows them to gain a deeper understanding of instructional strategies, student engagement techniques, and classroom management skills. Through this active learning process, pre-service teachers can develop their own teaching style, build confidence in their abilities, and establish a strong foundation for their future career in education. Additionally, the teaching internship offers pre-service teachers the opportunity to establish professional relationships within the education community. These relationships can be invaluable for networking, mentorship, and future job opportunities.

Experiential learning is a key component of the teaching internship, as it allows pre-service teachers to apply their knowledge and skills in real-world situations (Ramirez, 2020). It provides them with the opportunity to engage in reflective practice, adapt their teaching strategies, and develop effective classroom management techniques. Furthermore, experiential learning during the teaching internship allows pre-service teachers to understand and address the diverse needs and abilities of their students. Overall, the teaching internship is an invaluable experience that prepares pre-service teachers for their future careers by providing them with practical skills and knowledge in a real classroom.

In the context of the Philippines, the teaching internship plays a crucial role in preparing pre-service teachers for the challenges and realities of the local education system. It provides them with the opportunity to work in diverse classroom settings and gain

firsthand experience in addressing the specific needs of Filipino students. During the teaching internship, pre-service teachers in the Philippines have the chance to implement culturally responsive teaching strategies and develop a deep understanding of the Filipino culture, values, and educational practices (Fabelico and Afalla, 2020). By immersing themselves in the local education system, pre-service teachers become better equipped to cater to the unique needs of Filipino students and create inclusive and equitable learning environments. Furthermore, the teaching internship in the Philippines allows pre-service teachers to actively engage with the local community and understand the social, economic, and cultural contexts that influence education. This understanding enables them to design relevant and impactful lessons that resonate with their students' experiences and backgrounds.

Practice Teaching Internship

The practice teaching internship is a valuable opportunity for students to gain practical experience and apply their theoretical knowledge in a real-world setting (Yoto et al., 2020). It allows them to develop essential skills such as lesson planning, classroom management, and student assessment. Furthermore, the practice teaching internship provides aspiring teachers with the opportunity to observe experienced educators in action and learn from their expertise (Mutiara et al., 2020). Through the internship, future teachers have the chance to immerse themselves in educational activities, actively engage in frontline teaching, and gain valuable hands-on experience.

Additionally, the internship ensures that future teachers have a comprehensive understanding of the teaching process by involving them in all stages, making it a mandatory requirement for all participants (Nghia & Tai, 2019). During the internship, students will have the chance to work closely with mentor teachers who will provide guidance and feedback to help them refine their teaching techniques. This real-world experience is crucial for building confidence and competence in future educators. By participating in the internship, students will also build relationships with their students and gain a deeper understanding of the diverse learning needs within a classroom setting. Overall, the practice teaching internship equips students with the practical skills and confidence they need to excel in their future teaching careers. The internship program provides physics students in teacher training and education faculty with the opportunity to practice and develop their soft skills, which are essential for effective teaching (Susilawati et al., 2020).

The practice teaching internship in the Philippines is an integral part of teacher education programs. It is a crucial step towards becoming a licensed teacher and is typically undertaken during the final year of a bachelor's degree in education. During the practice teaching internship, student teachers are assigned to a partner school where they work closely with cooperating teachers or mentors. The internship serves as a bridge between theory and practice, allowing student teachers to apply their knowledge in a real classroom setting. They can observe experienced teachers, assist in lesson planning, and deliver lessons under the supervision of their mentors (Fresko & Wertheim, 2015). The practice teaching internship also provides an opportunity for student teachers to develop their soft skills, such as communication, classroom management, and problem-

solving. Lastly, the practice teaching internship in the Philippines is a valuable and necessary component of teacher education programs, providing future teachers with the opportunity to gain practical experience.

Challenges in Teaching Internship

One of the main concerns is that the internship may not fully prepare students for the challenges they may encounter in actual classroom settings. The controlled environment of the internship site may not accurately reflect the complexities of real-world teaching, where educators often face diverse student needs, behavioral issues, and other unexpected challenges. Additionally, some critics argue that the emphasis on fulfilling internship requirements may overshadow the focus on deepening the students' understanding of educational theories and pedagogical principles. This could lead to a prioritization of fulfilling practical requirements over developing a comprehensive and critical understanding of teaching and learning.

Furthermore, the practice teaching internship may also place a significant burden on schools and mentor teachers. Schools may need to allocate additional resources to support and supervise student teachers, which could potentially disrupt the daily operations of the educational institution. Mentor teachers may also face challenges in balancing their own responsibilities with the task of guiding and monitoring student teachers, potentially impacting the quality of their own teaching and mentorship. It is essential to consider these opposing perspectives when evaluating the effectiveness of practice teaching internships and to continuously assess and improve the internship program to address these concerns.

One challenge is ensuring effective communication and coordination between teacher education programs and collaborative schools. This is crucial to ensure that the goals and expectations of both parties align, and that the internship experience is meaningful and valuable for student-teachers (Parveen & Mirza, 2012). Another challenge is providing adequate support and guidance to student-teachers during their internship. This includes providing mentorship, feedback, and resources to help student-teachers navigate the demands of the classroom and develop their teaching skills. The dynamic nature of the practice teaching internship program necessitates a critical reflection on its impact and a commitment to continuous adaptation and improvement. This reflective process involves examining the inherent strengths and limitations of the internship experience, as well as considering the evolving demands and expectations within the educational landscape (Moore, 2020).

Connecting Theory and Practice

While the practice teaching internship effectively bridges the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application, it is imperative to delve deeper into how this connection can be further strengthened. Emphasizing the integration of educational theories and pedagogical principles within the internship curriculum can enhance the depth of understanding for student-teachers (Sukhovienko et al., 2020). By fostering a comprehensive and critical approach to teaching and learning, the internship experience

can align with the broader goal of cultivating educators who are well-equipped to address the multifaceted challenges of the classroom.

Moreover, engaging student-teachers in meaningful discussions and analyses of educational theories and research can facilitate a more nuanced understanding of overarching educational principles (Wang, 2020). This study discussions and analyses of educational theories and research can facilitate a more nuanced understanding of overarching educational principles. This approach not only complements the practical aspects of the internship but also instills a sense of intellectual curiosity and scholarly inquiry within aspiring educators.

Empowering Collaborative Schools and Mentor Teachers

As the practice teaching internship program places demands on collaborative schools and mentor teachers, it is essential to empower these stakeholders through tailored support and professional development opportunities. Collaborative schools can benefit from capacity-building initiatives that equip them to effectively supervise and mentor student-teachers while balancing their own instructional responsibilities. Additionally, fostering collaborative networks among mentor teachers can facilitate knowledge exchange and best practice sharing, enhancing the quality of mentorship provided to student-teachers (Datnow & Hubbard, 2015). By acknowledging the pivotal role of collaborative schools and mentor teachers, the internship program can cultivate mutually beneficial partnerships that prioritize the holistic development of student-teachers within the context of a supportive and nurturing educational ecosystem (Duşe et al., 2017).

Thus, the practice teaching internship program in the Philippines embodies both promise and challenges, presenting an opportunity for continuous refinement and enhancement. By prioritizing critical reflection, theoretical integration, and adaptability, the internship program can evolve into a robust platform for the holistic development of future educators and the enrichment of collaborative school environments (Dewsbury & Brame, 2019).

Research Questions

This study was aimed to reflectively describe and analyze the lived experiences of the Pre-Service teachers in their internship in Manuel A. Roxas High School. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the challenges and experiences of the Pre-Service teachers in their internship in Manuel A. Roxas High School?
2. What are the themes and insights that can be analyzed and interpreted from the narratives of the co-researchers?
3. What are implications and recommendations that can be derived from the insights and findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

This study used a qualitative approach utilizing a phenomenological design. Phenomenology is a study approach that aims to investigate the phenomenological perception from the standpoint of the individual who had the experience (Giorgi, 2009). The goal of phenomenology is to describe the significance of an experience in the context including both how and what was experienced. Clark Moustakas (1990), and Max van Manen (1994) are both experts in phenomenology who developed phenomenological methodologies to examine lived experiences. Ramirez (2017) expounded on the steps in doing phenomenology and asserted the primacy of lived experiences in theorizing on the phenomenon in question.

Selection of the Participants/Co-Researchers

The participants were selected based on the following criteria:

- Pre-service teachers in different learning areas
- Studying in Adamson University
- Having their teaching internship in Manuel A. Roxas High School
- Willing to share their lived experiences

Table 1. Profile of Participants of the Study

Name	Gender	Course and Major
Ruth Anna Q. Aguja	Female	BSED - English
Mica Carmen Banzuelo	Female	BSED - English
Scarina Carino	Female	BSED - English
Mark Darius Garin	Male	BSED - English
Jemark Pilapil	Male	BSED - English

Data Gathering Tool

In the area of this research study, lived experience is defined as a person's perceptions and interpretation of their own experiences, alternatives, and possibilities, as well as how they shape one's understanding perspective. The data of this research were collected through an interview. Interview is an open-ended, discovery-oriented method to obtain detailed information about a topic from a stakeholder. In-depth interviews are a qualitative research method; their goal is to explore in depth a respondent's point of view, experiences, feelings, and perspectives (Sahoo, 2022).

Data Gathering Process

The researcher used the steps of intuiting, analyzing, and describing the lived experiences of the students as postulated by Spiegelberg (1975). These steps were narrowed down as follows:

1. First Step: Gathering of Lived Experiences:

The researcher transcribed each student's experiences, which they obtained from them. The researchers assigned the interview a title that encapsulated the story's major point or theme after transcribing it. They additionally requested that each co-researcher provide an emblem that represented themselves in their experience.

2. Second Step: First and Second Reflections – Textual and Structural Themes:

The significant units or core concepts were established at this step to characterize the narrative's qualities in the first iteration. This was said in a single word, phrase, or sentence. Then, the researchers expanded on the interpretation established by connecting and merging the textual themes of the co-researchers based on similarities, closeness, or common organizing principle to build a structural theme. There may be times when themes intersect due to their interwoven character, in which one is linked to the others and to the whole. As a result, themes with comparable meanings and connections will be blended into one.

3. Third Step: Third Reflection: Essential Insights and Eidetic Insight

The researchers derived several ethical concepts or Fundamental Insights/Postulates from the first and second phases of contemplation, which when synthesized produced the elements of the Eidetic Insight.

4. Fourth Step: The Possibilities:

In this part, the main researcher elaborated on the varied forms by which the eidetic insight might be applied to various domains or fields articulating thus, the implications and recommendations were formulated.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Structural Themes

Adaptability and Resilience

Each narrative touched on the need to adapt to new environments and overcome challenges. Whether it's transitioning from private to public schooling, adjusting to

different teaching methods, or dealing with unexpected changes, the Pre-Service Teachers demonstrated resilience and adaptability in their approaches.

"Being an intern at a public school was shocking. I have a hard time adjusting since the culture is not the same as Adamson's." – Ruth Anna Q. Aguja

"It was challenging but also enjoyable... I was culture shocked because, unlike in public, students in private schools are easy to read and understand." – Mica Carmen Banzuelo

The narratives highlighted how adaptability and resilience are critical traits for educators. Facing the challenge of transitioning between different educational settings, especially from private to public institutions, requires flexibility and perseverance. This adaptability not only assists in personal growth but also prepares them to handle diverse classroom environments and unexpected situations in their teaching careers.

Mentorship and Support of the Cooperating Teachers

The role of mentors or cooperating teachers or faculty members, is crucial in their narratives. The support and guidance from experienced educators helped the interns navigate their teaching experiences and grow professionally.

"When I stepped at Manuel A. Roxas High School and got a teaching experience with the guide of my incredible Cooperating Teacher Ma'am Mary Jane Angeles..." – Scarina Carino

"The most memorable part of my teaching internship is that post meeting every after whole day class. When Mrs. Jandusay will give her assessment on how we did on that day." – Mark Darius Garin

The significant role of mentors in shaping future educators is evident across the narratives. Effective mentorship provides Pre-Service Teachers with a safety net and a wealth of knowledge, enabling them to learn best practices and avoid common pitfalls. This support is crucial in helping interns build confidence and refine their teaching skills, underscoring the importance of strong mentor-mentee relationships in educator preparation programs.

Professional Identity Development

Each Pre-Service Teacher discussed their journey of self-discovery and professional growth. The internship experience played a crucial role in helping them see themselves as educators and understanding the responsibilities that come with the profession.

"I like being called 'Sir' because it sounded professional and respectful at the same time. I like being with students because they are like shining armor to me..." – Jemark Pilapil

"I am also challenged by the teachers' work because I was shocked by how much work a DepEd teacher has."- Mica Carmen Banzuelo

Developing a professional identity is a transformative process that unfolds throughout the internship experience. As the Pre-Service Teachers navigated through their roles and responsibilities, they begin to internalize what it means to be a teacher. This journey helped solidify their commitment to the profession and aligns their personal values with their professional responsibilities, contributing to a stronger sense of self and purpose.

Challenges in Student Engagement

Managing and engaging a diverse classroom is a recurring challenge. The narratives discussed various strategies and struggles related to maintaining discipline, motivating students, and adapting teaching methods to meet the needs of all learners.

"From my students, it was challenging to manage a class that consists of 45 students and above per section given they have different personalities." – Ruth Anna Q. Aguja

"There are many times my students are noisy, but I will keep silent until they shut their mouths." – Mark Darius Garin

Engaging in diverse classes is one of the most common challenges faced by interns. This theme reflected the need for creativity, patience, and innovative teaching strategies to address varying learning styles and behavioral dynamics. Successful engagement affects student outcomes and satisfaction, highlighting the need for teachers to continuously develop their skills in this area.

Value of Education

There is a strong emphasis on the nobility and importance of the teaching profession. Despite the challenges and societal perceptions, the Pre-Service Teachers recognized the impact they can have on their students' lives and the broader community.

"Teaching is a noble profession, it is more than a profession rather than a passion." – Scarina Carino

"I just liked the idea of passing on knowledge and shaping and molding young minds." – Mica Carmen Banzuelo

Despite societal underestimations and financial concerns, the Pre-Service Teachers' narratives reflect a profound recognition of the intrinsic value of teaching. They see education not just as a job but as a calling to influence future generations positively. This perspective is crucial for maintaining motivation and dedication amidst the challenges of the profession.

Community and Cultural Sensitivity

The Pre-Service Teachers often reflect on the importance of understanding and integrating into the community culture where they teach. This sensitivity to cultural and socioeconomic backgrounds helps them better connect with their students and their families.

"The culture and environment in public schools reflect the real situation of education in the Philippines." – Jemark Pilapil

"Despite my initial culture shock, I thoroughly enjoyed my time at Manuel A. Roxas High School." – Mica Carmen Banzuelo

Understanding and integrating into the community where one teaches is vital for effective education. The Pre-Service Teachers' experiences show how cultural sensitivity can enhance the learning environment and facilitate better relationships with students and their families. This awareness promotes inclusivity and equity within the classroom, ensuring that all students feel valued and understood.

Personal and Emotional Growth

The internships are not only professional learning experiences but also personal journeys. The narratives revealed significant personal and emotional growth, such as increased confidence, empathy, and a deeper understanding of student-teacher relationships.

"After student teaching I noticed that I became more confident. I also developed my skills in communication, listening, collaboration, adaptability, empathy, and patience during student teaching." – Scarina Carino

"Resiliency and Open-mindedness; there was one time that every day was exhausting and even when I rest, my energy is still not replenished." – Mark Darius Garin

The emotional and personal growth that accompanies the internships is profound. Dealing with various challenges not only builds professional skills but also fosters personal qualities such as empathy, patience, and resilience. These qualities are essential for teachers, who must not only educate but also support their students' emotional and social development.

Essential Insights

The Critical Role of Adaptability in Teaching

Teachers must be highly adaptable, able to adjust their teaching styles and strategies to meet the needs of diverse classrooms and unexpected situations. This includes transitioning between different types of educational settings, such as moving from private to public schools, and adapting to various student behaviors and learning preferences. Adaptability is not just about coping with different classroom settings; it's about thriving

in them. The ability to swiftly adjust teaching methods to engage students effectively is a vital skill that improves student outcomes. Teachers who are flexible and responsive to the dynamics of the classroom can better support their students' learning and manage challenges more effectively.

Mentorship Enhances Professional Growth

Strong mentorship is invaluable for novice teachers. Guidance from experienced educators can accelerate professional growth, providing new teachers with insights into effective classroom management, lesson planning, and student engagement strategies. Cooperating Teachers serve as role models and provide a support system that helps novice teachers navigate the complexities of their profession. This relationship is crucial for building confidence and competence, as mentors can offer both corrective feedback and moral support. Effective mentorship also helps induct new teachers into the cultural and community norms of their schools, which is essential for their success.

Interconnectedness of Emotional and Professional Resilience

Teaching requires both emotional and professional resilience. The ability to manage one's emotions in the face of professional challenges is as crucial as developing teaching competencies. Teachers often face emotional challenges, such as dealing with difficult classroom situations, balancing personal and professional life, and sometimes facing disrespect or lack of cooperation from students. Building emotional resilience allows teachers to remain focused, optimistic, and effective in their roles, thus fostering a positive learning environment and maintaining personal well-being.

Cultural Sensitivity Strengthens Community Bonds

Understanding and respecting the cultural backgrounds of students enhances the effectiveness of teaching and strengthens the relationship between schools and their communities. Teachers who are culturally sensitive are better equipped to create inclusive classrooms that respect diverse backgrounds and learning needs. This sensitivity helps in designing lessons that are relevant to the students' experiences, promoting engagement and participation. Moreover, teachers who engage with the community and show respect for its norms and values can foster stronger partnerships with parents and community leaders, further enriching the educational experience for students.

Conclusions

Eidetic Insight:

Teaching internship is a dynamic journey of continual adaptation, emotional resilience, mentor-supported growth, and cultural engagement, which collectively shape the professional identities and effectiveness of the Pre-Service Teachers

The eidetic insight captures the essence of the Pre-Service Teachers' experiences as detailed in their narratives. Each element mentioned—adaptation, emotional resilience, mentorship, and cultural engagement—plays a crucial role in the development of a teacher. Teaching is not a static profession; it demands ongoing learning and adjustment to various challenges and environments.

Adaptation refers to the practical ability to modify teaching methods and approaches in response to different classroom settings and student needs, ensuring that learning remains effective and inclusive. Emotional resilience highlights the personal growth teachers undergo as they navigate the emotional complexities of the profession, from managing stress to building meaningful connections with students. This resilience is critical in maintaining a positive and productive classroom atmosphere and in safeguarding the teacher's own mental health. Mentorship is another cornerstone of professional development for teachers. Through the guidance and support of experienced educators, novice teachers gain confidence and skills that are crucial for their success and satisfaction in their roles. Mentors provide not only technical teaching advice but also serve as role models and supporters in the often-challenging early stages of a teaching career.

Lastly, cultural engagement enhances a teacher's ability to connect with their students and community, fostering a deeper understanding that goes beyond the academic content. This engagement ensures that teaching practices are sensitive and responsive to the cultural backgrounds and values of the students, which enhances learning outcomes and builds stronger community ties. In all, these elements form the foundation of a nurturing, effective, and responsive teaching environment, as demonstrated through the transformative experiences of the student teachers in their narratives.

Recommendations

Based on the insights and reflections focusing on the challenges and growth of pre-service teachers during their internships at Manuel A. Roxas High School, here are some tailored research recommendations:

- 1. Enhance Mentorship Programs** – Develop structured mentorship programs that provide pre-service teachers with continuous support from experienced educators throughout their internships. This could include regular feedback sessions, joint planning, and reflective discussions that help interns integrate theory with practice

more effectively. As the research highlighted, effective mentorship is crucial for professional growth and confidence building among pre-service teachers.

- 2. Focus on Cultural Sensitivity Training** – Implement comprehensive cultural sensitivity training within the pre-service teaching curriculum to prepare teachers for the diverse classroom settings they will encounter. The research indicated that cultural sensitivity and community engagement are important for creating inclusive and effective learning environments. Such training can improve understanding and interactions with students from various backgrounds.
- 3. Strengthen Experiential Learning Opportunities** – Expand opportunities for experiential learning by incorporating more hands-on teaching experiences, simulations, and classroom management exercises within the teacher education program. Experiential learning is vital for understanding classroom dynamics and developing effective teaching strategies, as evidenced by the interns' experiences.
- 4. Support Emotional and Professional Resilience** – Include workshops and seminars that focus on developing emotional resilience and stress management techniques for handling the pressures of teaching. The challenges faced by interns often included emotional stress and the need for resilience. Supporting this aspect can enhance teacher well-being and efficacy.
- 5. Regular Assessment and Feedback** – Create mechanisms for regular assessment and feedback during the internship, allowing pre-service teachers to receive constructive criticism and praise in real-time. Continuous feedback helps in rectifying mistakes early and reinforces good teaching practices, contributing to professional growth.
- 6. Collaborative Learning Environments** – Encourage collaborative learning environments where pre-service teachers can share experiences, challenges, and solutions with peers. Collaboration fosters a supportive community among Pre-Service Teachers, enhancing learning through shared experiences.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Phenomenology subscribes to the principle of utmost respect for the subjects of research. The respect is manifested in soliciting the co-researcher's formal acceptance to be part of the study. The co-researchers were provided an informed consent letter requesting from each their cooperation. They are asked a permission to take photos, to video-tape or audiotape their voices. The researcher did nothing beyond what had been agreed

upon. The co-researchers expressed their consents to use their actual names in the thematic analysis. There was an assurance that the matters disclosed will not be used for any other purpose except for information that will promote their good and amplify the contributions of gays to the quality of life in our society. They were asked to choose if the interview will be virtual or face-to-face while following safety protocols and measures.

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